

Single shot vaccine for multi-use: An overview

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Abstract

Vaccine research is supported by related fields like microbiology, biochemistry, and immunology. These lead to development of new vaccines for immunization of many diseases. In the pipeline there are more than 500 vaccines which are being extended to some form of peanut allergy, coronary artery diseases, cervical cancer, blindness, gastric ulcers, diabetes etc. New Vaccines against HIV, TB and Malaria are developing by researchers are still under development process because knowledge in some other areas are also important. Many traditional vaccines require multiple injections to provide effective patient protection these lead to costly and inconvenient regimen which gives a idea about single shot vaccines. The single shot vaccines can provide protection with only one injection for curing diseases¹. During the development and manufacturing process of single shot vaccines the complex factors must be controlled for a significant influence on efficacy of immune response. Single shot vaccination concept is widely applicable to different types of antigens and vaccines. In future the research is required to know the adjuvants influence and release characteristics in different vaccination regimens.

Keywords: Vaccine; Immunology; Antigen; Adjuvant; Microspheres

1 Introduction²

Vaccine is part of a virus or bacteria this is exposed for your body in a secure and effective way. It is usually a weakened or dead part of the germ. Then, in case you stumble upon the ones germs on your body everyday, the immune system will know exactly how to combat them off. while a germ or pathogen does enter your body, your immune machine fast acknowledges there's an interloper and works to save you it from spreading. because the immune system embarks on this attempt, it makes specialized reminiscence cells that can don't forget a pathogen or germ. Vaccines are generally made by using injecting sufferers with a slight form of the disease or separating parts of the disease-inflicting microbe to familiarize the immune machine with how the disease works so it could combat it. There are different forms of vaccines, each protect against certain illnesses, but method stopping infection in exceptional methods. Different types of vaccines are mentioned in table-1.

Vaccines make a contribution extensively to enhancing international health by prevent the debilitating, and in some cases, fatal effects of infectious illnesses through inducing a protective immune response towards the causative agent. Vaccines' fulfillment is confined, however, by the want for a couple of injections, and because this costly and inconvenient routine regularly ends in logistical demanding situations and bad affected person compliance. latest advances in the use of biodegradable microsphere-based structures show the capability of growing single-shot vaccinesto conquer this obstacle. By combining a prime and booster dose in one injection the single-shot vaccines are obtained.

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Table 1 Different types of vaccines

S.no	Types of vaccines	working of vaccines	Examples
1	Live-attenuated vaccines	Live attenuated vaccines basically inject someone with a much less strong form of the disease they're trying to guard towards (hence: calling it "live"). This in turn receives the body's immune machine used to the ailment and allows it to generate its personal immune reaction. because this vaccine is so effective, you normally only want such a vaccines in an entire life — not like yearly vaccines.	Chicken pox, Measles, Yellow fever, Smallpox
2	Inactivated vaccines	Inactivated vaccines are like live vaccines besides they incorporate a lifeless form of the disorder. because they aren't live, they have a tendency to now not be as potent and you will likely want a booster shot to "improve" the vaccine's effectiveness.	Flu (shot version), Polio, Hepatitis A, Rabies
3	Subunit, recombinant, polysaccharide, and conjugate vaccines	These vaccines, instead of the usage of the complete microbe that causes a disease, rip it aside and pick out smaller quantities of it to create a extra particular immune reaction.	HPV, HepB, Meningococcal (Meningitis), Whooping cough
4	Toxoid vaccine	Toxoid vaccines use what a disease's microbe produces to create an immune reaction. So essentially it renders the germ risk-free by using neutralizing the germ's toxic output.	Tetanus, Diphtheria
5	DNA Vaccines	DNA vaccines are the brand new breakthrough in the subject of immunization and are quite unique from traditional vaccines. In DNA vaccines, the genes responsible for causing the sicknesses, (the genes coding for the antigenic protein) are diagnosed and remoted from the pathogen and integrated into a vector (plasmid) carrying the gene into the dwelling device. The plasmid sporting the gene is injected into the muscle cells and is translated into antigenic protein that elicits the immune response normally caused via the pathogen.	Herpes Simplex Virus- 2, Bacillus anthracis, Hepatitis B, Multiple sclerosis
6	Transgenic plant vaccines	Transgenic plants are used as vaccine production systems. The genes encoding antigens of bacterial and viral pathogens may be expressed in plants in a shape wherein they keep native immunogenic properties	Rabies, hepatitis B virus, vibrio cholerae, HIV virus.
7	Sugar glass vaccine	Blending the vaccine's stay viruses with two sugars, sucrose and trehalose. the mixture is then dried out on a plastic film and hardens into glass. inside the sugar-glass, the vaccine is immobilized and kept in suspended animation. To put together the vaccine for injection, the glass is flushed with water and speedy dissolves, reactivating the vaccine.	Measles, influenza tetanus vaccine
8	Skin patch vaccine	Skin patch with micro needles delivers the antigens into the skin of patients	Cholera toxins, flu vaccine, dengue vaccine

9	Combination of vaccines	Combining of live and killed antigens of different organisms to prevent more diseases by giving only one time vaccination.	MMP(Measles-Mumps-Rubella),DTP(Diphtheria-Tetanus-pertussis)
10	Immunomodulation delivery	Immune responses can be modulated by using new adjuvants and cytokines, thus diseases can be prevented	Hepatitis B, auto-immuno diseases.

2 The single-Shot Vaccine concept

The single-shot vaccine is a mixture manufactured from a top factor—antigen with the correct adjuvant—and a microsphere issue that encapsulates antigen and offers the booster immunizations with the aid of behind schedule launch of the antigen. Many components want to be taken into consideration when developing such managed release era-primarily based vaccines.

Figure 1. Injectables formulation

2.1 Adjuvant mode of action

Adjuvants are essential for activating and improving the adaptive immune responses towards vaccine antigens and their reaction may be mediated through B and T cells. Interactions of adjuvants with Antigen imparting Cells (APCs) cause secretion of numerous cytokines, which stimulate and differentiate B cells into reminiscence B cells for lengthy-time period immunity and plasma cells for the manufacturing of antibodies in opposition to the brought antigens.

Adjuvants show their results in different approaches. The adjuvant including alum and emulsions (e.g. MF59, AS04) mainly act by using depot effect for the encapsulated antigens at the injection site and launch antigens slowly for longer time period, which keeps the activation of the immune system. These kinds of adjuvants beautify endurance of antigen on the injection site thereby growing the infiltration of antigen supplying cells. Adjuvant such as alum can form multi-molecular aggregates with antigens and attract APCs at the site of injection. Different adjuvants, including microbial additives act as ligands for pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) and induce innate immunity by way of focused on APCs. After interacting with PRRs, downstream signalling components along with transcription factors are activated main to generation of effector cytokines. The secreted cytokines and chemokines play an essential role in priming and expansion of the immune cells. occasionally, interactions of an adjuvant including MDP to NOD like receptors can also activate inflammation some pathway through secretion of IL-1 β . Few adjuvants can directly have an effect on the antigen presentation through modulating the binding of antigens to major histocompatibility complex (MHC) molecules. Class of modern vaccine adjuvants are mentioned in table-2.

The microsphere element makes use of OctoPlus's proprietary OctoVAX microsphere era, which is based on cross-linked modified dextran polymers. Dextrans are best polymers to shape biocompatible hydrogels. two predominant blessings of dextran microspheres as protein shipping structures are that the debris are prepared inside the absence of organic solvents, and that degradation of the microspheres does not result in a pH drop. each exposure to natural solvents and an acidic surroundings are regarded to negatively affect protein stability. numerous one of a kind dextrans were evolved for hydrogel formation. this kind of dextran-based totally polymers is derivatized with hydroxy-ethyl methacrylate (dex-HEMA) which introduces hydrolytically sensitive carbonate ester organizations that make sure biodegradation underneath physiological conditions³. studies have shown that protein therapeutics developed with this polymer keep the hobby of the encapsulated protein following encapsulation and release.

Table 2 Modern vaccine adjuvants class

S.no	Adjuvant class	Example of adjuvants
1	Bacterial Products	Monophosphoryl lipid A* Klebsiella pneumonia glycoprotein* Bordetella pertussis* Bacillus Calmette-Guérin* V. cholerae and E. coli heat labile enterotoxin* Trehalose dimycolate CpG oligodeoxynucleotides Cell wall skeleton of Mycobacterium phlei (Detox®)* Muramyl dipeptides and tripeptides Threonyl MDP (SAF-1)* Butyl-ester MDP (Murabutide®)* Dipalmitoylphosphatidylethanolamine MTP*
2	Cytokines and Hormones	1,25-dihydroxy vitamin D3 Interleukin-1 Interleukin-6 Interleukin-12 Human growth hormone β2-microglobulin Lymphotoxin Interleukin-2* Interferon-α* Interferon-γ* Granulocyte-macrophage colony stimulating factor* Dehydroepiandrosterone* Flt3 ligand*
3	Carriers	Hepatitis B virus core* Cholera toxin A fusion proteins CpG dinucleotides Heat-shock proteins Fatty acids Tetanus toxoid* Diphtheria toxoid* Meningococcal B outer membrane protein (proteosomes)* Pseudomonas exotoxin A* Cholera toxin B subunit* Mutant heat labile enterotoxin of enterotoxigenic E. coli*
4	Living Vectors	Rhinovirus Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus Yersinia enterocolitica Listeria monocytogenes Shigella Bordetella pertussis Saccharomyces cerevisiae

		Vaccinia virus* Canarypox virus* Adenovirus* Attenuated Salmonella typhi* Bacillus Calmette-Guérin* Streptococcusgordonni* Herpes simplex virus Polio vaccine virus
5	Mineral Salts	Aluminum (“Alum”) Aluminum hydroxide* Aluminum phosphate* Calcium phosphate*
6	Polyanions	Dextran Double-stranded polynucleotides
7	Polyacrylics	Polymethylmethacrylate Acrylic acid crosslinked with allyl sucrose (Carbopol 934P)
8	Surface-Active Agents and Microparticles	Cochleates Dimethyl dioctadecyl ammonium bromide (DDA) Avridine (CP20,961) Vitamin A Vitamin E Nonionic block polymer surfactants* Virosomes* Saponin (QS-21)* Meningococcal outer membrane proteins (Proteosomes)* Immune stimulating complexes (ISCOMs)*
9	Unique Antigen Constructs	Multiple peptide antigens attached to lysine core (MAP)* CTL epitope linked to universal helper T-cell epitope and palmitoylated at the N terminus (Theradigm-HBV)*
10	Vehicles	Liposomes* Biodegradable polymer microspheres Lactide and glycolide* Polyphosphazenes* Beta-glucan Proteinoids Water-in-oil emulsions Mineral oil (Freund’s incomplete)* Vegetable oil (peanut oil)* Squalene and squalane* Oil-in-water emulsions Squalene + Tween-80 + Span 85 (MF59)*
11	Miscellaneous	Transgenic plants* Human dendritic cells* Lysophosphatidyl glycerol

	Stearyl tyrosine Tripalmitoylpentapeptide N-acetyl-glucosamine-3-yl-acetyl-L-alanyl-D-isoglutamine (CGP-11637)* Gamma insulin + aluminum hydroxide (Algamulin)*
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*Identifies adjuvants administered to humans

2.2 Formulation of single-Shot Vaccines^{4,5}:

Vital factors in the manufacture of a microsphere-based totally vaccine are excessive encapsulation efficiency and a steady particle-manufacturing procedure. Several formulation parameters play an important role in acquiring a robust process. The procedures and device used to manufacture numerous formulations. Dex-HEMA has been shown to be very appropriate for the formation of the hydrogel that facilitates managed release of encapsulated proteins. A microsphere components process has been evolved based on this polymer.

Figure 2 Schematic representation of the microsphere formulation manner

On this technique, an emulsion of aqueous dex-HEMA solution is formed in an aqueous polyethylene glycol (PEG) answer, by way of mixing them in a bioreactor vessel. To make sure consistently excessive encapsulation efficiencies, the protein to be encapsulated is brought to the dex-HEMA answer before adding the PEG answer. ultimately, microspheres are obtained by way of polymerizing the HEMA corporations the usage of potassium persulfate (KPS) as initiator and N,N,N',N'-tetramethylethylenediamine (TEMED) because the catalyst. After huge washing, the final microsphere suspension can be stuffed into vials and freeze-dried to stabilize the product.

2.3 Factors effecting the microsphere formulation⁶

Numerous elements are essential parameters for the method of steady microspheres. First, the scale distribution of the microspheres may be managed through the shear pressure carried out at some stage in the emulsification step within the bioreactor vessel. Factorsthat have been identified to persuade this shear force are the mechanical stirring speed inside the bioreactor vessel and the viscosity of the PEG answer, that is decided by using the concentration and molecular weight of the PEG.

Second, the presence of excipients within the starting composition can influence the matrix density and encapsulation efficiency of the microsphere product, both by using a direct effect on the microsphere formation or on the protein traits.five subsequently, polymerization situations including KPS awareness, pH, and temperature, can have an impact on the energy of the shaped hydrogel matrix.

2.4 During Process Scale-up Controlling of Particle Size:

The dextran microsphere instruction technique^{7,8}, defined with the aid of Stenekes et al., four changed into first of all performed on a 5-g scale (containing a hundred and twenty mg of microspheres), and used vortexing as a means to emulsify the dex-HEMA phase in the continuous PEG segment. But, vortexing isn't always practical at large scale. Therefore, they evaluated the feasibility of stirring, a system this is enormously easy to scale up, as a method of

emulsification, in the long run at a 500-g scale. a direct correlation become located among stirring velocity and mean particle diameter of the microspheres, for this reason confirming that the particle size of the dextran emulsion is depending on the energy enter during emulsification.

It is essential to be aware that, regardless of the bigger suggest diameter of microspheres organized at the 500-g scale, more than 90% of the ensuing particles had a size beneath ninety μm , a length appropriate for subcutaneous injection. To optimize the stirring manner, the production set-up became transferred from ordinary laboratory equipment and glassware to an autoclavable 2-L jacketed bioreactor unit geared up with baffles and a stirring assembly. The production system has now been scaled up to at least one, 500 g with a production of miscrospheres averaging forty μm in length.

2.5 Delayed Release of Antigen from Dex-HEMA Microspheres ^{9,10}:

As soon as the freeze-dried microsphere product is rehydrated by means of reconstitution in an aqueous solution, hydrolysis of the carbonate ester companies inside the dex-HEMA can be initiated. this will increase the mesh length within the hydrogel network. The encapsulated protein could be launched when the mesh size exceeds the hydrodynamic diameter of the protein. The real launch profile of the encapsulated protein is usually decided with the aid of the matrix density.

It has been shown that the release of proteins and liposomes can be tailored from days to months by using various the main elements influencing the matrix density, which are the relative range of HEMA agencies in dex-HEMA (degree of substitution, DS) and the initial water content of the microspheres. The consequences of various DS and initial water content on in vitro launch profiles of a version protein, IgG, are presented. maximum different microsphere delivery technologies, which includes the poly-lactic-co-glycolic acid (PLGA)–primarily based transport era, include technique steps that reveal the protein to doubtlessly damaging natural solvents.

In contrast, the OctoVAX microsphere formula is a totally aqueous system, which limits the outcomes of producing at the integrity of the encapsulated proteins. Furthermore, due to the open matrix of the microspheres, hydrolytic degradation does now not induce local acidification which can affect the protein's hobby. As a part of our unmarried-shot vaccine improvement application, in a mouse version that the efficiency to result in an antibody reaction is similar between encapsulated HBsAg and freely injected HBsAg. Thoserecords suggest that the HBsAg particle domain names that result in those antibody responses aren't suffering from the formulation system or with the aid of the discharge method.

3 Conclusion

The idea of single-shot vaccination is relevant to diverse kinds of antigens and vaccines. The development of a single-shot vaccine technology may want to make a contribution to a massive boom in vaccination insurance global by improving affected person compliance and decreasing management expenses. To achieve this innovation, single-shot vaccines should be rationally designed. To facilitate this, complex factors inside the improvement and manufacturing method which have a extensive influence at the efficacy of the immune response ought to be controlled precisely in the course of the development and production phases. A further study is needed to research the affect of adjuvant and release traits in numerous vaccination regimens.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Y udayabhaskarrao, recent advances in vaccinology; Indian j.biotech, 2003,2, 494-498.
- [2] Van de Weert M, Hennink WE, Jiskoot W. Protein Instability in Poly(Lactic-co-Glycolic Acid) Microparticles. Pharm Res. 2000;17(10):1159–67.

- [3] Van Dijk-Wolthuis WN, Tsang SK, Kettenes-van den Bosch JJ, Hennink WE. A new class of polymerizable dextrans with hydrolyzable groups: Hydroxyethylmethacrylated dextran with and without oligolactate spacer. *Polymer*. 1997;38(25):6235–42.
- [4] Cadée JA, Brouwer LA, den Otter W, Hennink WE, van Luijn MJ. A comparative biocompatibility study of microspheres based on crosslinked dextran or poly(lactic-co-glycolic)acid after subcutaneous injection in rats. *J Biomed Mater Res*. 2001 Sept 15;56(4):600–9.
- [5] Vlugt-Wensink KD, de Vruueh R, Gresnigt MG, Hoogerbrugge CM, van Buul-Offers SC, et al. Preclinical and clinical in vitro in vivo correlation of an hGH dextran microsphere formulation. *Pharm Res*. 2007;24(12):2239–48.
- [6] Franssen O, Hennink WE. The preparation of dextran microspheres in an all-aqueous system: effect of the formulation parameters on particle characteristics. *Pharm Res*. 1998;15(4):557–61.
- [7] Vlugt-Wensink KD, Meijer YJ, Steenbergen MJ, Verrijck R, Jiskoot W, et al. Effect of excipients on the encapsulation efficiency and release of human growth hormone from dextran microspheres. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm*. 2007;67(3):589–96.
- [8] Stenekes RJ, Loebis AE, Fernandes SM, Crommelin DJ, Hennink WE. Controlled release of liposomes from biodegradable dextran microspheres: a novel delivery concept. *Pharm Res*. 2000;17(6):690–5.
- [9] Chung JT, Vlugt-Wensink KD, Hennink WE, Zhang Z. Effect of polymerization conditions on the network properties of dex-HEMA microspheres and macro-hydrogels. *Int J Pharm*. 2005;288(1):51–61.
- [10] Stenekes RJ, Franssen O, van Bommel EM, Crommelin DJ, Hennink WE. The preparation of dextran microspheres in an all-aqueous system: effect of the formulation parameters on particle characteristics. *Pharm Res*. 1998;15(4):557–61.